

Stress tolerance

Weed competitiveness of upland rice cultivars in Bangladesh

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Upland rice is generally exposed to severe weed infestation. Vegetative vigor, large leaf area, plant height, and N absorption at early growth stages are related to the crop's ability to compete with weeds.

We conducted trials during 1989 and 1990 aus (wet season) to screen for suitable lines or varieties that can compete with weeds.

The soil is silty clay loam, with pH 6.5-6.8. Test entries in 1989 were BR4290-3-3-5, BR4290-3-1-10, IR255-88-7-3-1, and varieties Hashikalmi, BR20, and BR21. In 1990, we discarded BR20 and IR255-88-7-3-1 and used Kataktara as local check because Hashikalmi was unavailable. Test entries were grown under weed-free conditions as one treatment.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Seeds were sown on 3 May 1989 and 7 May 1990 at 100 kg/ha in lines, 20 cm apart, in 3 × 2.5-m plots.

Recommended fertilizer management practices were followed, with an additional 20 kg N/ha as urea applied at 58 d after emergence (DE) to meet the crop's demand. No insecticide was used.

Weed and plant heights were measured at 0, 42, 72, and 88 d after seeding (DAS). We recorded plant population at 39 DE in 1989, but in 1990, only 140 plants/m² were kept. In 1989, weeds were removed from 1 m², cleaned, oven-dried at 70°C for 72 h, and weighed, but in 1990, weeds/m² were counted. Leaf angle to the culm was measured at dough stage.

Major weeds were *Paspalum* sp. and *Echinochloa colona*. Minor weeds were *Cyperus iria*, *Cyperus rotundus*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Acanthospermum* sp., *Eclipta prostrata*, and *Commelina* sp.

Under water stress, rice seedlings did not emerge until 13 DAS in 1989; many weeds emerged before this, indicating their superiority in this condition. At 32 DE, rice entries were taller than the weeds (Table 1). Weed weight was lightest with Hashikalmi, possibly because the taller plants intercept more radiation (36.37%).

Plant heights significantly differed at maturity. Although grain yield production was not high under intense weed pressure, yield of BR4290-3-1-10 and BR21 was comparable to the local check (Table 1).

In 1990, rice seedlings emerged at 5 DAS. Weed seedlings emerged in the meantime, indicating a speed of germination higher than that of rice. Plant height, leaf angles, grain yield, and growth duration varied significantly because of rice-weed competition (Table 2). Reduced leaf angles in all test entries may be due to poor growth. The local check and BR21 were more erect, which allowed more light to penetrate. BR21 produced the highest grain yield in the weeded plot, but produced only 0.22 t/ha in the unweeded. BR4290-3-1-10 yield (0.51 t/ha) in the unweeded plot was significantly higher than that of the others. This line also performed well in 1989.

BR4290-3-1-10 is a promising line for uplands under weed stress but is inferior to BR21 under weed-free conditions. □

Table 1. Rice yield and some other parameters as affected by weeds, 1989 aus. ^a

Entry	Rice plant (no./m ²)	Height at 32 DE (cm)		Plant height at maturity (cm)	Weed wt removed (g/m ²)	Radiation interception (%)	Grain yield (kg/ha)
		Weed	Rice				
BR4290-3-3-5	176	26 a	35 a	71 b	215 b	27.10	374 b
BR4290-3-1-10	181	25 a	31 c	63 c	203 b	31.19	442 ab
IR255-88-7-3-1	193	19 b	34 bc	57 d	200 b	28.01	359 b
BR20	130	26 a	36 b	74 b	225 b	29.64	357 b
BR21	167	24 a	36 b	74 b	201 b	34.18	407 ab
Hashikalmi (local check)	296	27 a	46 a	91 a	132 a	36.37	647 a
CV (%)	25.3	10.4	5.2	6.1	30.2		18.2

^a Separation of means in a column by DMRT at P 0.05 level.

Table 2. Some plant parameters as influenced by weed competition. 1990 aus. ^a

Entry	Rice leaf angle (°)				Grain yield (t/ha)		Growth duration (d)	
	Second leaf		Flag		Unweeded	Weeded	Unweeded	Weeded
	Unweeded	Weeded	Unweeded	Weeded				
BR4290-3-1-10	11 ab	13 a	25 bcd	32 abc	0.51 d	1.39 b	88 d	93 c
BR4290-3-3-5	11 ab	13 a	37 ab	41 a	0.25 e	1.09 c	96 a	97 a
BR21	9 b	11 ab	24 bcd	32 abc	0.22 e	1.89 a	93 bc	96 a
Kataktara	9 b	10 b	13 d	18 cd	0.22 e	1.04 c	95 ab	95 a
CV (%)	13.6		12.3		16.2		1.3	

^a Separation of means across two columns – weeded and unweeded – by DMRT.